

Abstract: As olive is the most widespread fruit tree in Montenegro, eventual detection of the bacterium *Xylella fastidiosa* would cause great economic losses, besides implying the implementation of a permanent monitoring campaign. This is especially due to the importance of early detection of the bacteria as well as its vector(s) for the timely implementation of control measures to prevent it spreading. Given the significance of the vectors in the transmission of *X. fastidiosa* and the limited information about their presence in Montenegro, a study was undertaken to determine the species of Auchenorrhyncha (Cicadomorpha) present in olive groves on the Montenegrin coast. During 2018, insects were collected using sweep net sampling at three locations in the area of Valdanos and two locations in the area of Radanovići (Sampling was carried out on weeds, twice in the area of Valdanos (late May and late October) and once in the area of Radanovići (early September)). The collected insects were preserved in 96% alcohol until determination. Insect identification was performed on the basis of the morphological characteristics of the species. Sixteen Auchenorrhyncha species were identified of which 12 belong to the Cicadomorpha, three to the Aproclyptidae and nine to the Cicadellidae families. In all three locations in the area of Valdanos the most prevalent was *Philaenus spumarius* L. (main vector of *X. fastidiosa* in Europe) while *Lepyronia coleoptrata* (L.) was mainly collected in the area of Radanovići (.

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Phenology and host-plant selection of *Philaenus spumarius* in vineyards of north-western Italy

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Abstract: In order to contribute to the risk assessment of *Xylella fastidiosa* in vineyards, surveys of *Philaenus spumarius* were carried out in north-western Italy. A vineyard in Asti was sampled in 2016 and 2017. It was selected because of the ecological complexity of the site including grapevine rows, and herbaceous cover within and around the rows and broadleaved trees/shrubs surrounding the vineyard, as alternative hosts for the spittlebug adults. Nymphs and adults were sampled every 10 and 15 days, respectively, from the beginning of March until the beginning of December in both years. Nymphs were counted and their host plant identified, in herbaceous cover of vineyard headlands and inter-rows. Adults were sampled from three vegetation compartments of the vineyard: i) grapevine plants; ii) herbaceous vegetation (headlands and inter-rows); and iii) shrubs, trees and other spontaneous woody plants. Herbaceous cover was visually inspected for foam and nymphs, and each nymph was assigned to a life stage. Sampling of nymphs was done in randomly selected areas of 0.25 m², delimited by a rectangular frame. Adults were collected by sweeping net, counted, sexed, identified and immediately released. All samplings were conservative. Population dynamics and phenology, with respect to chronological and physiological time, were described for both nymphs and adults. Host plant selection of nymphs and vegetation compartments of adults are reported all over the two years. Five more vineyards in the Piedmont Region, besides the one in Asti, were inspected in 2018 using the same methodology, although surveys were carried out only three times in the season. The first survey was conducted in April, at the time of nymph population peak. The second and third surveys were aimed at sampling adults in June and September. Population abundance and host plant selection by nymphs, as well as population abundance and vegetation compartments of adults are reported.

Assessment of the genetic diversity in populations of *Philaenus spumarius* collected from different areas

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Abstract: The spittlebug *Philaenus spumarius* is a widespread species in Europe, recently attentioned because of its relevant role in spreading the plant pathogenic bacterium *Xylella fastidiosa* (Xf), a new emerging pathogen threatening the landscape and several crops in southern European countries. Being the main species associated with the epidemic spread of this bacterium currently decimating olive trees in the Apulia region (southern Italy), molecular investigations have been carried out to characterise the populations occurring in the so-called *Xylella*-demarcated areas of Apulia versus those present in other regions currently free from *X. fastidiosa*. Analysis also included specimens received from Montenegro and Tunisia.

Three DNA markers were used, the mitochondrial genes COI and cytochrome b and the nuclear gene EF1- α , to amplify and sequence DNA fragments from a total of 60 specimens. Mitochondrial sequence analysis showed that all Italian specimens belong to the south-west clade (which includes the Mediterranean basin and western Europe) and, in particular, the majority of the Apulian specimens and those collected in Montenegro belong to the eastern Mediterranean subgroup, whereas the specimens collected in other regions of Italy belong to the western Mediterranean subgroup. Conversely, the Tunisian specimens fell in the eastern group (Anatolia/Caucasus). Similar genetic relationships were retrieved from the analysis of the EF1- α gene.

The data herein obtained, while confirming that the population of *P. spumarius* responsible for the epidemic spread of Xf in Apulia belong to a single phylogenetic group, integrate the large dataset of biological and ecological information collected from the studies intensified on this species in the last few years.

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Predominance and natural infectivity of potential vectors of *Xylella fastidiosa* in olives in south-eastern Brazil

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Abstract: As xylem-feeders, several species of sharpshooter (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae: Cicadellinae) and spittlebug (Hemiptera: Cercopoidea) are potential vectors of the xylem-limited bacterium, *Xylella fastidiosa*, which is associated with olive quick decline syndrome (OQDS) symptoms in south-eastern Brazil. Here we investigated the epidemiological importance of these species based on faunal indices and natural infectivity with *X. fastidiosa* in olive orchards of the Mantiqueira Mountain Range (MMR) region, in São Paulo (SP) and Minas Gerais (MG) states. The insects were sampled with yellow sticky cards hung at two heights (0.8 and 1.6 m) on the outer branches of nine olive trees per orchard; the cards were replaced fortnightly from June 2015 to August 2017. Based on faunal analysis, those species classified as dominant, very abundant and very frequent were considered predominant. Samples (n=15) of three individuals of each predominant species were evaluated for the presence of *X. fastidiosa* by qPCR and conventional PCR. Out of 48 species (5,055 individuals) of sharpshooters and spittlebugs trapped in an orchard in São Bento do Sapucaí (SP), six are predominant (*Clastoptera* sp.1, *Amblyscartidia pardaliota*, *Macugonalia cavifrons*, *Paratubana luteomaculata*, *Scopogonalia paula* and *Subrasaca bimaculata*), whereas in an orchard in Maria da Fé (MG), 7 of 45 species trapped (2,026 individuals) are predominant: *Clastoptera* sp.1, *Bucephalagonia xanthophis*, *Erythrogonia*